

PEDAGOGICAL VIEWS, EDUCATIONAL AND UPBRINGING ISSUES
IN THE WORKS OF SADRIDDIN AINI.

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Abstract: This article provides a scientific and theoretical analysis of pedagogical views, educational and upbringing issues in the works of Sadriiddin Aini.

Keywords: books, children, pedagogical ideas, class essence, important service, practical activity, emir's government, parents, gifts and greetings, imams, mudarris, corporal punishment, etc.

One of the main places in Sadriiddin Aini's pedagogical views is the development of issues of moral upbringing of children. He considered discipline education to be an integral part of moral upbringing, understood it as the development of a conscious, active attitude to entrepreneurship and to each other. He strongly criticized corporal punishment and its use in the educational process.

Some books read in schools aroused a sense of fear and despair in children. The lessons were aimed at preventing children from thinking only about the afterlife, not about a happy and real life on earth.

Reading the ghazals of Hafiz, Jami, Bedil had almost no educational value for school-age children. These ghazals were love poems that had a negative impact on young students.

Sadriiddin Aini wrote: "When she finished reading the last lines in her deep voice, a thrill ran down my spine:

Either I die, or I will always be with her,
I have no peace ...

I knew nothing about love then, but I understood that there was some kind of sadness in her soul, and I wanted to do something to alleviate this sadness".

If children admit their mistakes and try to correct them, this is also useful for establishing discipline.

These moments of educational practice are reflected in Aini's works, where it is said that after the guest leaves, Sadriiddin comes to his father and admits that he did not fast, that he was lying. The father laughed and hoped that Sadriiddin would not lie again.

Sadriddin Ayni touches on another pedagogical issue here. In his opinion, if children admit their mistakes, they should not be scolded, but taught so that they do not repeat such bad deeds in the future.

In the issue of instilling good behavior in children, Sadriddin Ayni highly appreciated the role of encouragement. In his opinion, encouragement inspires children to further success and strengthens self-confidence.

Sadriddin Ayni wrote: "His (Sharifjon Makhdum Sadri Ziya) praise of my abilities encouraged me to go to Bukhara to study."

From the memoirs of his student Rahim Kashim, who studied at the first Soviet secondary school in Samarkand, it is clear that Sadriddin Ayniy was demanding and persistent as a teacher. They tried to respect the personality of children, to convince students of the wrongness of the offenses they committed. He gives various examples from people's lives to eliminate bad habits that have developed in children .

We consider it appropriate to cite the following episode from Sadriddin Aini's work "Memories" that shows the role of the example of the work of teachers and adults in the formation of a sense of hard work in children; This episode tells about the struggle of farmers with sand, the help of Sadriddin's father to his grandfather in cleaning the sand in the garden. After completing the main part of this work, Aini's father got ready to go home and said to his grandfather: "Okay, I'll go now. Your sons now know how to weave a fence without me. But removing all the sand from the garden is a long and difficult task. Start, your sons will finish."

Parents of modern children are literate and educated people, they have great opportunities to use this form of educational work in the family;

Sadriddin Aini believed that in order for labor to become a vital need for every child, children should understand that with their labor (albeit small), they help their parents and bring benefits to the family. For this, Sadriddin Aini believes, children should feel and understand the needs of the family.

"Now the question arose about sending me to Bukhara to study, but my father found it very difficult to support his two sons in the Bukhara madrasah. He suggested that I earn the money I needed to study and live in Bukhara myself" – recalls Sadriddin Aini.

This forced Sadriddin to do something to help the family and achieve his goal.

Sadriddin Ayni also touches on another side of the issue: in order to properly organize labor education, there must be a clear goal. A set goal encourages children to do useful work.

At the same time, in some families, parents believe that if they themselves lived in poverty and worked very hard, then their children should spend more time on the street and waste their time throughout their lives.

Such views of some parents on raising children are alien to the task of preparing the builders of modern society. They treat physical labor in children with contempt;

Building a modern society requires people not only knowledge, but also the ability to work.

In Sadriddin Ayni's pedagogical views, his ideas about the mental development of children occupy one of the main places. He considers the upbringing of children to be the sacred duty of every parent. His father's dying will is very characteristic in this regard.

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